

EXPRESSION OF TEMPORAL MEANING IN VERB PHRASES OF ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES

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Abstract.

The English language has its own system of structural grouping and signals of the phrase. The phrase is the combination of two or more words which is a grammatical unit but is not an analytical form of some words. The constituent elements of a phrase may belong to any part of speech. A phrase must contain at least two national words. Each component of a phrase can undergo grammatical changes in accordance with grammatical categories represented in it, without destroying the identity of the phrase.

Our graduation paper is about the verb phrase which express a temporary relation in English and Karakalpak languages.

Key words.

structural group, phrase, elements of phrase, temporal meaning in verb, compare.

Introduction. The study of verb word combinations with temporal meaning in the English and Karakalpak languages in comparative terms is of scientific and practical interest.

To express the temporal meaning in modern English, there are various models of verb phrases: verb phrases without a preposition according to the V+n model and verb phrases with prepositions according to the model \ /+pr+n. A comparison of the factual material shows that the same transitive verbs in combination with nouns of different semantic groups can form phrases of different nature. Most verb-nominal phrases with transitive verbs as a verb component express object relations. But these same transitive verbs, when combined with nouns with a temporal meaning, form phrases with a temporal meaning. For example:

to study English - inglis tilin úyreniw (objective meaning)

to study in the morning - azanda oqıw (temporal meaning)

Non-prepositional phrases with a temporal meaning are of great interest for research, because they especially clearly trace the dependence of the general meaning of the phrase on the lexical meaning of the components as a whole. In

prepositional phrases, a large role in the expression the preposition plays the general meaning of the phrase.

The use of an intransitive verb as a leading component is more typical for the phrase of a non-preposition with a temporal meaning. In such phrases, the nominal component is placed directly after the verb, if there is no adverb of place. For example: When they came back to the ranch he had been dead and week - olar farmağa qaytıp kelgeninde onıń opat ekenine bir hápte bolıp edi.

English prepositions of circumstances of time form a small system based on the opposition of groups of prepositions to each other, individual prepositions within the subgroups that form each group, and on the opposition of individual prepositions to groups. At the same time, the nature of oppositions is relative.

If there is a definition before the names of the parts of the day, then instead of the preposition "in" "on" | am planning to finish it in February; On Sunday evenings at eight they met.

In this case, the opposition is relative. In English, temporal relations are expressed with the help of prepositions, it should be said that prepositions with temporal meanings indicate different periods of time;

1. Corresponding phenomena, facts, actions to a certain moment or period of time.
2. Precedence of actions, facts, phenomena to a certain moment or period of time.
3. Consequence of actions, facts, phenomena to a certain moment or period of time.

These relations, expressed by the prepositions of the English language, are expressed. In the Karakalpak language with the help of case affixes and postpositions or in a lexical way.

The meaning of English prepositions with a temporal relation in the Karakalpak language is expressed in three spatial cases.

1. Dative-directive;
2. Initial;
3. Local.

Numerous meanings of English prepositions do not have a single functional-grammatical correspondence in the Karakalpak language. They can correspond to the following grammatical means.

1. Postpositions (postpositions-particles, postpositions-names).
2. Case affixes.
3. Lexical means.

The analysis of the practical material showed that there were cases when the English preposition was omitted when translating into the Karakalpak language,

This phenomenon is connected with the norm of the Karakalpak language. Since the semantic integrity of the sentence is not violated. Thus, the analysis of the translation of English prepositions into the Karakalpak language allows us to come to the following conclusions: the English preposition, being a function word, plays an important role in modern English when linking significant words in a sentence.

Similarly to the English language, postpositions-particles, postpositions-names, case affixes are performed.

Analysis of the transmission of English prepositions with a temporal relation to the Karakalpak language allows us to say that English prepositions in the Karakalpak language do not have a single direct grammatical correspondence. English prepositions with a temporal meaning are more quantitative in composition than Karakalpak postpositions expressing temporal relations.

Our analyzed material shows that most of the prepositions of modern English in the meaning of temporality correspond in the Karakalpak language to postpositions and case affixes.

For a better assimilation of all the given meanings of prepositions, it is necessary to constantly compare not only similar, but also different forms of their expression and identify both similarities and differences in the grammatical forms of the two languages. Such comparisons will help Karakalpak pupils and students to learn the meanings of English prepositions in all their diversity in phrases, to apply them correctly in practical work, on the language.

This work can be used as a practical and theoretical material for teachers of secondary specialized educational institutions and general education schools of the republic. And also this work is very useful when writing courses and final works of students.

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